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Communication and the Quality of Human Relations: (A reflection of Cell phones and enhancement of the quality of Human relations)

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ABSTRACT

The world has shrunk in size. It has become a global Village. There is no distance in communication. The revolutionary discoveries and innovation in communication technology has taken the world of humans to the skies. He is in contact with person to person; point to point, second to second and place to place. Be it cell phones in his palm or the internet, he is able to reach out to any one on any point on the globe. This paper tries to discuss whether or not the communication has enhanced the quality of human relations? The extent to which, it is functional and dysfunctional and the possible repercussions for the human society and human relations. The paper is based upon two small studies conducted on cell phone usage among Student community and professionals. The paper draws the conclusion that given the limited frugal usage of cell phones would certainly enhance the quality of human relation its overindulgence as in the case of students is certain to produce negative consequences detrimental to humans and the human habitat including the birds and other living beings for whom it might cause harm.

Keywords: Communication, cell phones, home, road, college

Introduction

Today communication is the life line of human beings more so after the liberal usage of cell phones by humans. Today rich and poor, rural or urban we hardly see any man without cell. Even the man it has certainly aided his sociability. Soliloquy was some that one murmurs to oneself. That was considered as a sign of mental stress blue tooth. Today one would mistake a lone walker with headphones on or with the partially visible blue tooth may be mistaken for talking to oneself. No man is alone at least by communication wise. He

converses with some one or the other. The advancement in communication has increased sociability. I am tempted to alter Aristotle's definition of humans as "Man is a cell animal". Cell is in every palm making it as the essential instrument of human existence.

Objective

This paper tries to discuss whether or not the communication has enhanced the quality of human relations? The extent to which, it is functional and dysfunctional and the possible repercussions for the human society and human relations.

Method of Study

The paper is based upon two small studies conducted on cell phone usage among Student community and a group of professionals.

The paper draws the conclusion that given the limited frugal usage of cell phones would certainly enhance the quality of human relation its overindulgence as in the case of students is certain to produce negative consequences detrimental to humans and the human habitat including the birds and other living beings for whom it might cause harm. Technology does aids humans by enhancing his quality of his life. To make it as a boon or bane is in our hand the analysis of the data gathered, in both the studies as well as the keen observation of the authors have driven home the following facts regarding the impact of cell phones on human relations.

At Home

1. One telephone for each house normally was the normal practice and multiple phones was only very few rich homes. Today phone has become an individual property. Some even have two.
2. Phone was placed at one corner of the house but phone now is in the hands of every one.
3. To talk to friends over phone needed timing and talking to many for longer time invited snaring and reprimands from parents at home. Today one can slip into bathroom and converse for hours. Privacy it has emerged.
4. It has increased the family's budget on communication. The land line also in its place to only for incoming calls.
5. It has disturbed the tranquility of the home with the ring tones.
6. Cell has enhanced the quality of the communication. Be it the web cam or the 3 G phone one can see the person on the other end on the tiny screen

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- adding the feeling of face to face conversation. The boundaries are crossed in seconds. Even the waiting seconds entertains the
7. Caller by a tune and the callers are denoted by specific caller tones.
 8. Parents' anxieties are over. They can now know where their wards are. The delays in arrivals and leaving are timely conveyed to ward off anxieties and fears. Children are telephonically followed till they reach their destination.
 9. Even spouses follow each other to know their whereabouts. The spousal anxiety is thing of the past.
 10. There used to be a time for phoning. Either it used to be in the mornings before 6 a.m. and after 9 pm when pulse rates used to be less. Even the STD telephone booths are not to be seen.
 11. It is now possible to make ISD calls from cell phones. Virtually the world has shrunk to one' own palm.
 12. The men carry the cells in their belts or pockets; women in their bags and girls in their palms. They may forget their jewels but not their cells any more.
 13. Silence used to be the grace in women but any more after the invasion of the cell. They are talking and talking whole country has garrulous. Bhol India Bhol.

On the Road

1. Man behaves as if he is talking to the person face to face with gesticulation.
2. Man tells many a time lays denying the place where he is and what he is doing when he answers his cell calls.
3. The anytime calling has put man in peril when he is drives his bike and car.
4. Cells have become causes for accidents on the road not noticing the fast approaching vehicles.
5. The peace and tranquility is disturbed. The ring tones fill the air. The noise pollution is the legacy cell phone addition to the world.
6. The cell towers have become the perching points for monkeys and crows. In the place of trees we find cell trees. For some it has becoming the suicide threatening towers.
7. The posture of thinker no more signifies man rather man with his elbow towards his ears represents man.
8. For the trader it aids his business. It has reduced merchants waiting time and booking time.

9. On the road it can catch a crime suspect report crime or pass on info on crime and can be a crucial impersonal witness, averting the revenge of the criminal.
10. The driver of the bus intimates the departure of the bus and conveys the reasons for the delay.
11. And the reservation position and the vacancies. Some do the reservation over cell phones save tickets. The railway reservation can be updated over phone.
12. The android phone can guide the path to go in a strange area with GPRS software.
13. Interactions have now need to be classified as face to face vocal verbal, face to face silent SMS)
14. Distant vocal verbal (Phone) distant non silent verbal (SMS). Any way man is social he keeps on interacting with fellow humans.
15. It is the ready walkie talkie and it is the ready handy camera to catch a rare glimpse.

In the College

1. It is the communication machine more important books and
2. Note books. It is the status symbol of the student.
3. It aids copying if unchecked. It is a store house of information (Nos of friends)
4. It stores glimpses, portraits. Photo album.
5. It has brought into existence a new language of texting with admixture of numbers and words by passing grammar rules.
6. It is a means of harassing the girls with obscene texts.
7. It is a handy calculator and torch at need.FM radio and a games it is the gadget to drive away drudgery.
8. The android mobile, is a creative machine using one' finger.

For the elders their wards are the prime callers.

For the youngsters, their friends are their prime targets of communication.

For the old their children and grand children are the only contacts.

For the businessman and the trader it is the cheap mode of advertisement.

It propagates messages, alarms and messages.

The cell has shown a new avenue of employment for the smart business man. Cell business is thriving. It intoxicates. Today man cannot go without cell. It comes next only to shelter.

Today man maintains double identity with two Sims.

It comes in different shapes and costs.
Cell phone and Human relationships:

1. It helps in verbal non verbal communication. It stretches human relation beyond face to face with same length of intimacy. Be it friends or lovers.
2. It has replaced greeting cards. It has come to relieve his boredom and loneliness.
3. It has emboldened him and her to be safe and cautious.
4. It has redefined communication. fine tuning it to point to point, place to place; person to person.
5. The cell savvy and communication savvy man has indeed become the cell animal.
6. The negatives are also worthy to mention along with its advantages.
7. The sparrows are gone unable to bear the frequency of the waves.
8. The power of silence has gone. People have become publically noisy. Privacy is lost.

The identity of man is in the 10 digits. No caste, religion or place. No doubt it has become a boon to mankind. No wires, No electricity needed. Any where the signals are there humans will talk: Communication has compressed time and place. It is up to us to make a judicious use of this gadget without ruining our habitat. Science and Technology are for the benefit of the mankind to give him better quality of life and a refinement of his relations with fellow humans and for his safety and peaceful coexistence with the flora and fauna.

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